

Modular Technology in Distance Learning

Author(s), I.U. NAZAROV

Abstract:

In this article, the features of modular learning are compared with the features of distance learning and the model of using modular technologies in distance learning is described in accordance with certain pedagogical conditions.

EASIJ

Accepted 25 August 2020

Published 31 August 2020

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4029057

Keywords: Informatization of education, distance learning, modular training, optimization, structuring, training content, training element, training module, principles of modularity, structural construction,

About Author

Author(s): I.U. Nazarov

Senior lecturer of the Department
"Information technologies" Tashkent
Nizami state pedagogical University, Uzbekistan.

The "action Strategy" for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 defines the most important tasks for updating the methodology, creating conditions for training qualified specialists at the level of international standards. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 2909 "on measures for further development of the higher education system" is aimed at increasing the level of reforms carried out in this direction.

The development of modern Uzbekistan requires the development of new innovative technologies in the teaching of subjects of higher pedagogical education. Improving education is impossible without the widespread use of modern information and communication technologies. In the light of these requirements, the modern system of higher education puts forward the task of using information and communication technologies as a necessary component of the professional activities of future specialists.

Currently, one of the tasks of Informatization of education, considered as a purposefully organized process of providing the sphere of education with methodology, technology and practice for the development and optimal use of information and communication technologies, is the creation of methodological training systems focused on the development of the intellectual potential of the student, the formation of skills to independently acquire knowledge, carry out activities for collecting, processing, transferring, storing information resources, and producing information [2].

At the same time, professional education becomes more accessible due to its "openness", thanks to distance learning, the ability to independently search for the necessary information from a distributed information resource on the global Internet and its use for educational purposes.

There is an opinion, both among teachers and among consumers of educational services, that distance learning is not a very high – quality form of education. However, research results and practice have shown that with a competent organization, the effectiveness of distance learning is comparable to that of full-time learning, all other things being equal [3].

Any theoretical model of a learning system (in particular, a learning system based on distance learning as a form of learning) can be described by five interrelated elements [1]: goals determined by a social order, content determined by current standards and technologies for a specific specialty, methods, organizational forms and means of learning.

Among the new technologies that have the required potential, modern pedagogical science distinguishes modular learning technology. Modular training the new generation of flexible education technologies and allows to solve complex tasks such as selection, optimization and structuring of learning content on activity basis; providing opportunities for divergent learning training content; specific portion presenting training material and step-by-step control of education; adapting training programs to the level of training of the trainee; quick correction and updating of the training content [4, 5, 6, 7, 8].

In modular technology, the learning process is implemented by dividing it into modules - professionally significant actions and operations that are performed by students more or less uniquely, which allows you to achieve the planned results. The development of each module by the trainee is made gradually. The implementation of each step is provided

with methodological manuals, which have received such names in modular technologies as «a training element» or «training module». The execution of each step is controlled with tests.

Any technology is predicted, organized and implemented on the basis of scientific principles, both General and specific. For modular technologies, researchers also identify the fundamental principles that define the goals, content selection, organization, and management of modular training. In our opinion, the most complete system of principles of modular training is revealed in the works of P. Yutsevichene [8]. These include the principles of modularity, activity, structuring the content into separate logically complete parts, dynamism, flexibility, conscious perspective, and parity of interaction between the teacher and the student.

Despite the long-term interest of science and practice in modular training, there is a lack of unified approaches to the conceptual and terminological apparatus, the allocation of conditions for the effective use of modular technologies, and the systematization of existing experience in their use.

However, it should be noted that the basis of all concepts of modular learning is an active approach which allows the learning process as a whole or within individual school subject is focused on the sequential assimilation of trainees of vocational or educational activities in accordance with the content of a modular training program.

Within the framework of various concepts, modular educational programs have different composition and structure, are presented in documents of various forms, but the three main components must include: a target content training program; a Bank of information in the form of packages of "Training elements" or "Training modules"; control packages that include tests and practical tasks.

If the potential and possibilities of modular technologies in the field of distance learning implementation are recognized by researchers, the theoretical and methodological bases of their application in this form of training are practically not developed. Thus, there is a contradiction between the objective feasibility of using modular technologies in distance learning and the lack of theoretical and methodological foundations for their design and organization, taking into account the specifics of distance learning.

The specifics of distance learning can be considered as follows: the educational process is based on computer telecommunications and provides for differentiation and individualization of learning; the system for monitoring the level of knowledge and skills acquisition is systematic and based on operational feedback; provides for the possibility of communication with the teacher in the process of cognitive activity; features of the technical and technological base require structuring and presentation of educational material in relatively small logically closed portions.

The correlation of this specificity with the features of the modular approach allowed us to identify the pedagogical conditions for the use of modular technology for distance learning.

To the allocated pedagogical conditions include: modular technology of education retains its essence consists in preparing the trainee to perform certain actions, which characterize the activity-based subject or professional training; learning content is presented in a modular programme with a flexible structure consisting of separate modular units,

adequate dedicated to operations, which, in turn, consist of training modules (training elements); the volume, structure and ways of presenting information in training modules depend on the specific educational material; the control system includes input, current, intermediate and final testing, is implemented using computer telecommunications, and a system of indirect control of the learning process is used, focused on technical and technological means of distance learning.

In accordance with the selected pedagogical conditions, a structural and functional model for the application of modular technologies in the remote form was developed. The model is considered in two aspects: content and organizational (technological). In the content aspect, it is a training program, the educational material of which is structured into separate modular blocks that have integrity and articulability. Each module block, in turn, includes training material necessary for the formation of knowledge and skills to perform a specific operation. The module block is structured into training elements. The educational element is the carrier of a portion of educational information of a theoretical or applied nature [4, 5, 6]. for each educational element, training goals are formulated, educational material is selected and well-illustrated, tests or practical tasks are compiled.

In the organizational aspect, the model reveals the process of implementing a modular program in a distance learning environment, which consists of installation, training, and certification stages. At the installation stage, the invariant modular program is individualized and adapted to the level of readiness of each student based on the results of the entrance test. The received individual modular program is presented to the trainee. At the training stage, students consistently study the educational elements included in their individual programs, pass the current control of assimilation of the content of educational elements and intermediate control of the content of modular blocks, perform control work. Training and supervision are accompanied by the necessary consultations of students by the teacher. During the certification stage, students perform, and teachers review and evaluate complex certification works, or a comprehensive final test or exam is conducted. Interaction between the teacher and the student at all stages, providing students with the content of educational elements, control tests, transfer of completed works by students to the University is carried out both by means of computer telecommunications and mass media.

The designed model can be used as the basis for developing a modular distance learning technology.

In accordance with the selected pedagogical conditions and the structural and functional model of the application of modular technologies in the conditions of distance learning, the tasks of developing modular software and methodological documentation were solved. To solve these problems, two variants of implementing the structural and functional model of using modular technologies in the conditions of distance learning were developed.

In the first version of the structural-functional model implementation, partially mediated interaction between the teacher and the student is assumed on the basis of computer telecommunications. In this version, the structural and functional model in the content aspect is implemented using a package of educational software and methodological documentation, compiled in accordance with the modular approach. The training program is based on the analysis of the content of those activities that are formed in the course of

studying this discipline (for example, solving problems, performing experimental research, performing design and technological works, etc.). the Program is structured into modular blocks, which, in turn, consist of educational elements. In our opinion, it is convenient to present a modular curriculum for distance learning in the form proposed in the concept "Training using modules of work skills" [8]. This form is a table with the names of module blocks in the horizontal rows and the names of training elements in the vertical columns. The belonging of educational elements to a modular block is indicated on the table field by conventional signs of compliance (see the version of the modular training program presentation form).

Training elements (UE)	UE 1	UE 2	...	...	UE n
Modular unit (MB)					
MB1	√		√	√	√
MB2	√	√			√

Figure 1. Presentation of the modular training program

This form of the program allows you to see the future of training and serves as a kind of content of the module manual (electronic or traditional).

Each training element in the modular program consists of three blocks: coordinating, which indicates the didactic goals and names of related training elements; informational, presented in the form of short, divided illustrated texts; controlling, containing tests and practical tasks.

In the organizational aspect, this option is implemented as follows. At the installation stage, the teacher conducts an entrance control. Based on its results, the modular program presented in tabular form is adapted to the level of preparedness of each student. This is done by "crossing out" from the program those educational elements, the knowledge of which the student discovered during the entrance control. Each student is provided with an individual training program and recommendations for its study.

Thus, we see that modular learning technology is based on such important didactic principles as the principle of consciousness and activity, the principle of systematicity and consistency, the principle of strength, the principle of accessibility and, of course, the principle of science. Taking into account the fact that the teacher can also connect theory and practice in modular lessons, we can safely apply this technology and its elements in distance learning.

List of used literature

- Piskala A.M. Methodical system of teaching geometry in primary school: Avtoref. Doct. dis. – Moscow, 1975. - 32 p.
- Robert I.V., Polyakov V.A. Main directions of scientific research in the field of Informatization of professional education. www.informatika.kspu.ru/mproj/umk/frameindex.html
- Tatarinova M.A. "Theoretical bases of creation and use of a distance learning course of foreign language written speech for 2-3 courses of a linguistic higher education institution". Author Dis. Cand. PED. n. - M., 2005
- Borodina N.V., Goronovich M.V. Training of personnel of educational institutions to organize the process of modular training. - Yekaterinburg, 1999.
- Borodina N.V., Samoilova E.S. Modular technologies in professional education. – Yekaterinburg, 1997.
- Krosche E. Guide to the modular system of vocational training. - Geneva, 1996.
- Choshanov M.A. Flexible technology of problem-modular training. - M.: National education, 1996.
- Yutsevichene P.A. Theory and practice of modular training. - Kaunas: Sviesa, 1989.
- Nazarov I.U., Tajibayeva M.Z. on the effectiveness of modular technology in school. Moscow-center for advanced scientific publications, 2019. – 66
- Nazarov I.U., Payazov, M.M. & Tadjibayeva, M.Z. (2019). Technology is getting rid of the noise in speech perception. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences,7 (12), 1133-1137.

Cite this article:

Author(s), I.U. NAZAROV, (2020). “ Modular Technology in Distance Learning”, **Name of the Journal:** Euro Afro Studies International Journal, (EASIJ.COM), P, 105 – 111. DOI: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4029057 , Special Issue, Issue: 2, Vol.: 2, Article: 11, Month: August, Year: 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.easij.com/all-issues/>

Published By

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

